

A Re-Examination of the Evolution of the Nigerian Capital Market Aromolaran L.A. Osun State College of Technology Esa-Oke Nigerian	133-141
The Role of Regulatory Bodies Capital Market Development The Nigerian Experience Prof. Remi Adeyemo Lead City University, Ibadan.	142 - 154
Participatory Governance in Ghana' decentralization Process And The Retrogression of Legislative Encroachment Kwamena Ahuioi	156-180
Measuring The Extent of Gender Segregation in The labour Market: Evidence from Ghana William Baah - Boateng	181-200
Issues and Challenges of Online Journalism Education in Nigeria Prof. Olufemi Onabajo Lead City University, Ibadan Dr. Cecilia Oladipo University of Lagos, Lagos	202-214
Socio - Economic Determinants for Adoption of Computer Assisted Learning Method Among Senior Secondary School Students in Ibadan, Nigeria. Ileuma Senimetu (Ph.D) University of Ibadan Nigeria Erwat Eseza Akiror (Ph.D) Lead City University Ibadan Isah Emmanuel Alleono Khnoya University of Ibadan	215-224
Assests Management: Acquisition and Control Techniques for Corporate And Public Organisation S.F. Akinbuli University of Lagos	225 - 238
Developing Thinking Skills of Nigerian Children Dr. Esther A.Oduolowu & Dr. Adekolarin Adewole University of Ibadan	239 - 252

THE ROLE OF REGULATORY BODIES IN CAPITAL MARKET DEVELOPMENT:

THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE

PROFESSOR REMI ADEYEMO

LEAD CITY, UNIVERSITY IBADAN, NIGERIA.

With the wave of economic liberalization across the globe, the issue of appropriate regulatory mechanism for capital markets and indeed financial markets as a whole has come under focus in some countries. To some market observers, the introduction of new regulations when financial markets are undergoing liberalization seems contradictory given that liberalization is characterized by policies which encourage greater freedom and less government control. We have seen for instance, that in the former command economies of Eastern Europe the transition to market-oriented economy has brought the establishment of capitalist institutions such as stock exchange and other capital market institutions has in turn necessitated the setting-up of statutory regulatory agencies to regulate the activities of market participants in some of these countries. Also drawing from the experience of the United Kingdom, financial market liberalization in the late 1980s ushered in new regulations and establishment of the Securities and Investment Board (SIB) - the statutory market regulator. In essence, economic or financial market liberalization may compel the introduction of more regulations. Why then is regulation necessary?

The need for capital market regulation is motivated by the desire to protect the investing public from malpractices, instill confidence in the system and ensure financial market and economic stability which are pivotal to economic growth and development. History has shown that inadequate or absence of regulation is detrimental to the capital market as it encourages sharp practices by participants (e.g investors, operators and issuers). Regulatory agencies are therefore necessary to police activities in the market with the ultimate aim of preventing or minimizing abuse which might mar investors confidence, the market's integrity and stability. As financial markets get liberalised, market participants are more likely to abuse the system hence new and sometimes stiffer regulations are usually introduced to prevent likely abuses, and keep the market in check. This in part accounts for the introduction of additional regulations in economies being liberalized. Regulations are nothing more than rule, principles and procedures which guide the conduct of all participants in the market. They are in other words, the dos and don'ts expected of any player in the market in order to achieve orderliness in the

market place and general stability. To ensure conformity therefore, sanctions must be incorporated in the regulations. Capital market regulations must not be excessive or absent as both situations would be detrimental to its growth and development. What is required is adequate and effective regulations capable of promoting confidence and stability, and stimulating participation. Obviously the continuous participation of investors in any capital market is largely predicted upon the reposal of confidence. Thus any action which erodes confidence would in turn create apathy as no investor would be enthusiastic to put his money in a market which is prone to abuses. It is also worthy to note that to attract foreign investors, a market must be seen to be essentially free from abuses and maintain an acceptable level of stability. The safety of investment is very vital, and this evidently explains the wariness of foreign investors about investing in unregulated markets. As was rightly concluded in an article titled: "Market Mania" the August 3, 1992 Edition of Newsweek Magazine, **"The New York Stock Exchange is a bastion of free enterprises and one of the most regulated markets on earth that is why it works"**

Types of Market Regulations: An unserved global trend is the adoption of a dual market regulatory structure with statutory and non-statutory regulations operating simultaneously. Non-statutory regulations (which lack legal backing) usually pre-date statutory regulations.

In most countries therefore, statutory regulations were introduced after the establishment of a formal market for secondary trading securities. On the other hand non-statutory regulations always evolve alongside the establishment of secondary facilities i.e. stock exchange and other-the-counter markets, in view of the fact that rules and regulations must be put in place from the onset to guide the mechanism of trading and general conduct of members. In a few markets such as Taiwan and Mauritius however statutory regulations were introduced prior to the establishment of stock exchanges. This might have arisen from the desire to have a proper legal framework in place at the evolution of a market place.

Statutory regulations are usually administered by securities commissions or similar bodies set up by government to oversee activities in the capital market. In countries where such bodies are presently non-existent, regulatory responsibilities usually fall on specific government ministries such as Minister of Finance or Economy. Evidently, most countries have

preferred the establishment of regulatory agencies with reporting responsibility to the Finance Ministry.

Non-statutory regulations are formulated and administered by Self-Regulator Organisations (SROs) and as indicated earlier such regulations have no force of law.

Role of Regulatory Bodies in Nigeria: Nigeria currently has two regulatory bodies viz: the Securities and Exchange Commission which has statutory powers and the Nigeria Stock Exchange with non-statutory powers. A third non-statutory regulatory body - the National Association of Securities Dealers - provided for in the enabling law of the Securities and Exchange Commission is yet to come into being. The two existing regulatory institutions have independently and collectively played vital roles in the development of the Nigerian capital market. It should be noted that while in developed markets regulatory bodies are principally concerned with markets regulation an emerging market such as Nigeria cannot but give equal prominence to market development. The peculiar feature of emerging markets make this essential. We look here at some of these features which would be examined in more detail later.

- i. Illiquidity
- ii. Smallness in size
- iii. Low participatory level of the populace
- iv. Relatively low level of professionalism
- v. Inadequate market information, etc.

These inadequacies which are common in many emerging markets are absent in matured markets hence market regulation forms the only focus of activities in matured markets. The specific roles of the Securities and Exchange Commission and the Nigeria Stock Exchange will be discussed next.

Role of Securities and Exchange Commission:

1. **Regulatory Role:** The regulatory functions of the Nigeria SEC is not substantially different from those of its counterparts elsewhere (which mainly is that of investors protection). The protection of investors is fundamental and requires certain safe guards which are put in place by the SEC. Like other Securities Commissions, safeguards are ensured through inter alia the adoption of basic orthodox methods of market regulation.

These methods include registration, surveillance, investigation and enforcement. Through these and other activities of the SEC investors' confidence has been straightened and participation in the capital market stimulated. Indeed, the realization by investors that a body existed which stand to protect their interest from malpractices and other forms of abuses, would encourage some levels of participation. Nonetheless, it is only when a regulatory authority is seen by the public as an unbiased regulator which performs its functions credibly without fear or favour, that confidence can really be strengthened and participation enhanced. The SEC in Nigeria has been able to maintain these ideals. Its functions are enumerated below:

- (a) **Registration:** This function is derived from Section 6 (b) of the Securities and Exchange Commission Decree 1988 which imposes on the SEC the responsibility of registering "all securities proposed to be offered for sale to or for subscription by the public or be offered privately with the intention that the securities shall not be held ultimately other than by those to whom the offers were made" Section 6 (d) and 14 from which this responsibility is also derived, mandated the SEC to register all markers and operators in the capital market. As you may have heard from speakers before me, registration is one of the most potent instruments of investor protection as it enables Securities Commissions to critically assess the fitness or otherwise of all institutions and persons proposing to operate in the capital market. Ascertaining their suitability is critical to confidence building, given that any unscrupulous action could erode confidence and destroy the fabric of the market.

As the basic disclosure instrument, registration demands that accurate and comprehensive information be sought and obtained from prospective registrants. In Nigeria, information submitted must be sworn to before a Commissioner of Oath. That notwithstanding, the SEC endeavours to verify all information submitted to it. In addition a satisfactory police clearance is required from all prospective individual registrants (Whether sponsored by organizations or not). This in essence, is to prevent the participation of ex-convicts and criminals in securities business. Registration extends also to securities and issuers of securities to ascertain the worthiness of the former and the credibility of the latter. Given the fact that the capital market thrives on confidence, the issuance of worthless securities would result in financial loss to investors, dampen confidence and hinder capital market development. An important registration, disclosure and investor protection document is the prospectus. For every public offer of securities therefore, this document must be well vetted and approved by the SEC.

Through vetting the SEC makes sure that the information contents are full, adequate, and clear (i.e. not capable of misinterpretations) such that would assist an investor make a rational decision. The SEC determined the information content which must be supplied in a prospectus.

Registration is a continuous process thus periodic renewal is expected of certain registrants such as market operators and facilities. In addition, all major change; concerning the registration must be promptly disclosed to the SEC. This enables the SEC determine the continued suitability of registrants to engage in capital market business. A violation of the terms of registration can attract suspension or revocation of registration. As an evidence of authority to operate in the market, the SEC issues certificates to all registered operators and advise that they be displayed at conspicuous areas in their offices. In the same vein, investors are advised to deal only with registered operators. The SEC usually takes appropriate actions against any person or persons who solicits for investment business in the capital market without due registration. The number of operating institutions in the market has increased considerably standing at 247. Many of these institutions were established in the late 1980s/ early 1990s encouraged by deregulation of the Nigerian economy and the enlightenment campaign by the regulatory authorities.

Although the contribution of market operators to the national economy is assessed in monetary terms, the increase in their number has undoubtedly stimulate activities in the market and enhanced capital formation.

(b). Surveillance and Investigation: The maintenance of market ethics (i.e. principles and rules of professional conduct) as well as transparency, are paramount to the sustenance of confidence. As the watchdog of the capital market the SEC constantly monitors market activities to forestall manipulative and other illegal practices. SEC derives this power from Section 6 (c), (e) and (h) of its enabling law which states that it should:

- Maintain surveillance over the securities market to ensure orderly, fair and equitable dealing in securities;
- Protect the integrity of the securities market against any abuses arising from the practice of insider dealing;

- Create the necessary atmosphere for the orderly growth and development of the capital marker.

Pursuant to this section, the SEC employs a number of surveillance tools which include the requirement that information affecting issues and issuers in both the primary and secondary market be promptly released to the public and that no trading is affected on the basis of privilege information. Trading activities involving Key Officers of quoted companies and all those who by virtue of their position have access to unpublished price sensitive information of public quoted companies are therefore thoroughly scrutinized for possible act of insider dealing.

Market surveillance also takes other forms. Of particular importance is the monitoring of trading activities on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Since the SEC and Nigerian Stock Exchange are yet to be electronically linked, surveillance takes the form of physical presence of representatives of Surveillance and Investigation Division of the SEC at every trading session of the Stock Exchange. These staff are expected to monitor trading activities vigilantly and report back any suspected case of price manipulation of insider dealings for investigation. Sharp price movements and unusually large volumes of transactions are often targets for scrutiny. In cases of suspected abuses, the SEC promptly calls for detailed records of all parties to the deal for investigation.

Another surveillance activity is the routine checks carried out on the market operators to ensure that proper records are being kept and no breach of market rules and regulations have taken place. Such checks are usually without prior notice and any observed lapse is reported for prompt investigation. The SEC also expects the Stock Exchange to submit to it reports of all inspections carried out by it on its member firms.

Indeed such reports do guide the extent of the SEC's routine checks. For instance an extensive follow-up checks could be commenced on member firm if the SEC sees the need to do so following surveillance report submitted by the Stock Exchange.

Surveillance further entails the review of newspaper and other periodicals to detect for investigation any report which might suggest that violation of securities laws have occurred.

It should be pointed out that in the securities market, even rumours could be useful source of detecting actual acts of illegality and should therefore not be dismissed without due investigation. Similarly, all complaints must be thoroughly investigated.

In Nigeria, the Surveillance and Investigation Division initiated investigation on all complaints received by the SEC and reports its findings to management for necessary action. In view of the infrastructural problems, most complaints border on delay in receipt of shares certificates and dividend warrants.

(C). **Enforcement:** Ensuring strict compliance with the securities laws is considered a very vital function of the SEC, being overly essential to investor protection and market integrity. The Enforcement Division of the SEC is responsible for this function and works very closely with the Surveillance and Investigation Division. It is the duty of this Division to determine if a violation of the law has occurred and to recommend appropriate sanctions and other remedial actions are important as they not only induce confidence but also serve as deterrent to further violations.

In Nigeria, sanctions on proven cases of violations take various forms, depending of course, on the severity of violation. For very minor offences a warning might be appropriate while severe cases could attract withdrawal of license in which case the offender is barred from operating in the capital market. Also a court injunction can be sought or litigation instituted. Furthermore, violators can be compelled to disgorge proceeds from transactions, cease operation or may be suspended from engaging in capital market activities for a given period or time. Usually, sanctions become negative publicity for operators because of the adverse effect which they invariably, have on their business. As operators are first and foremost in the securities business to make a livelihood, any unfavourable publicity on any operator would reduce investors' patronage and significantly hamper operations and profitability. Indeed, in cases of severe sanctions the reputation of an operator could be damaged to the extent that his business activities outside the securities market would be impaired. These possible consequences are deterrents from engagement in illegal activities.

(d). **Rule Making:** Securities market must be guided by rules and regulations. As the administrator of the securities laws and the apex institution for the capital market, the SEC in Nigeria like others, formulate rules and regulations aimed at maintaining stability and inducing sustainable growth and development of the capital market with ultimate benefit to the national economy. In a rapidly developing capital market (with record increase and improvement in

the quality and types of instruments, facilities operators etc rules and regulations should change if need be to accommodate changing circumstances. For instances, renewed dynamism of a market could warrant the introduction of new rules and regulations, amendments or revocations, of existing law considered outdated in light of new developments. Rule making should therefore be seen as an on-going process and not static. Similarly capital market authorities i emerging markets should, given their level of development formulate rules and regulation: which can enhance the growth and development of their capital markets rather than stifle or retard growth. Thus while regulating, developmental issues should not be neglected.

The aforementioned regulatory mechanism (i.e registration, surveillance investigation and enforcement) if adequate, and efficiently discharged would be effective in promoting investors confidence in a market. This is because an awareness by investor that all prospective operators in the market would be critically scrutinized to prevent the participation of persons of questionable character as earlier stated will kindle their interest. In the same vein, the awareness that market activities are being closely watched to prevent abuses, and if abuses occur, swift and appropriate action will be taken, will also stimulate participation in the market and boost its growth.

(e). Regulating Business Combinations: According to Section 6 (g) of the enabling law of the SEC, the SEC is to review, approve and regulate mergers, acquisitions and all forms of business combinations" Section 8 further expatiates this function by requiring that an application be approved only such a business combinations in the findings of SEC will not "directly or indirectly" or in any other form, "substantially restrain competition or create monopoly". However. Section 8 (3) of the law exempts holding companies

- Acquiring shares solely for the purposes of investment and not for the purpose of using the shares by voting or otherwise to create or attempt to cause substantial restraint of competition or tend to create monopoly in any line of business enterprises". Also exempted under Section 8(4) are transactions effected by any agency or government with powers to do so. The SEC has a drawn-up procedural guidelines to be followed strictly by companies tending to undertake such activities. The following conditions must be fulfilled.

Filing of a pre-merger notice with the SEC;

Lodging of a formal application form in respect of the merger/acquisition with the SEC for consideration;

Ensuring that all post approval requirements expected from the company are complied with.

Detailed information and documents about the companies involved in the proposed merger/ acquisition etc must be submitted to the SEC to enable it take a position on the application.

2. Market Development Role: It was earlier that the level of economic development of emerging capital markets calls for the introduction of developmental policies and programmes. From the Nigerian experiences, such activities have proved to be positive in stimulating the growth of the capital market as well as in increasing the level of capital formation and economic development. Among the features of emerging markets which makes it imperative for regulatory authorities to embark on developmental

Auctions are:

- i. **Few Listed Securities:** The number of quoted companies are relatively small in emerging markets. Besides many companies which are listing are not, owing to the reluctance of their proprietors to seek quotation for fear of diluting holdings and consequently losing control. For instance, many entrepreneurs in developing countries hardly differentiate their personal finance from corporate funds. Thus, occasionally companies' accounts are made to finance personal expenditures such as holidays, children's school fees, wedding and funeral ceremonies. In effect, corporate and personal accounts are seen as the same. The fear that a change in corporate status would erode power over, and control of the company, in addition to the expectation of greater accountability, do discourage enterprises from going public. Furthermore, lack of adequate knowledge about the benefits derivable from using the facilities of the capital market compound the problem.
- ii. **Low Demand for Securities:** The low personal income level in some ability of market economies, lack of proper knowledge about securities markets, availability of more attractive alternative investment particularly money market instruments and real more attractive alternatives at market rates than capital market growth do outweigh the latter.
- iii. **Low Trading Activities:** In market where demand for securities outweighs supply (as in Nigeria), the tendency is for existing investors to hold on to their securities for the fear that if disposed of, comparatively investments might not be easily found for purchase.

The desire for dividends which principally motivates investment in the securities market in some countries (again in Nigeria) discouraged trading in the securities of companies with high dividend yield since holders of such securities are usually reluctant to sell. A consequence of these factors is that market float (i.e securities available for regular trading) is relatively small. In Nigeria, and I believe in a number of other emerging markets the holding of institutional investors are large but unfortunately hardly traded. Speculative activities are therefore virtually absent in many markets. This is worsened by inefficient clearing and settlement system.

Government also contributes to the inactivity in some markets by acquiring interest in quoted companies in sectors considered to be economically strategic. This is however, fast changing in many countries implementing economic reform programmes.

- iv. **Poor Infrastructural Facilities:** Infrastructural facilities which are extremely essential for economic and capital market development are in poor condition in many countries. Such facilities as telecommunication, electricity, supply, postal service are inadequate and inefficient. For instance, power failure could temporarily disrupt trading while inefficient postal services contribute to delays in the delivery system. Also poor telephone services hamper communications while the clearance and settlement procedures are cumbersome in some markets.
- v. **Illiquidity:** The infrastructural problems identified above, coupled with the reluctance of many investors to sell, lead to market illiquidity.
- vi. **Small Market Size:** The number of companies in emerging market is generally fewer than those in developed markets. Similarly the dollar value of their outstanding shares is relatively small; and considering the low trading activities, market capitalization is small.
- vii. **Low Level of Market Awareness:** The level of securities market awareness is low in many emerging markets and contributory to the supply of and demand to securities. In some of these markets, literacy rate is quite low and public enlightenmen materials and programmes where available, are only meaningful to the literate class. Indeed the workings and essence of the capital markets are little understood even b the literate class, thus impairing its growth and development.
- viii. **Lack of Timely and Easy Access to Information:** Adequate, timely, comprehensive and easy access to information are very essential to investment decision in the capital market. Unfortunately these are largely lacking in developing markets.

- ix. **Few Financial Instruments and Institutions:** The array of financial instruments available for trading in any market would definitely stimulate both supply of and demand for securities in the capital market. In many emerging markets however, the choice of instruments available to investors is usually limited. In the same vein the level of financial intermediation is relatively low while intermediaries are less competitive, efficient and innovative than their counterparts in mature markets.
- x. **Low Level of Market Automation:** The trend around the globe is, towards securities market. Automation as a means of improving efficiency. Owing perhaps to size, infrastructural problems, technical financial and other constraints, many emerging markets are yet to be automated.
- xi. **Closed Markets:** With the exception of a few, many emerging markets are still closed to direct foreign portfolio investment. In the 1980s indirect portfolio investment became popular with the proliferation of sovereign and regional funds. xii. **Unfavourable Government Policies:** Unfavourable policies can inter-alia take the form of placing permissible limit on dividend and capital repatriation thereby discouraging participation in the securities market and the economy. Furthermore, the provision of cheap credit in the money market (which albeit is intended to boost investment) can depress the capital market and create distortions in the financial market as short term funds would be diverted into projects needing long term capital. The preference for considerable large debt financial vis-à-vis equity funds has its negative implications for both the company and the economy. Many of the problem enumerated above also characterize the Nigerian capital market. Nonetheless, significant efforts are being made by both regulators and operators to improve the situation. Indeed remarkable progress has been recorded in this regard. Being empowered with the duty of fostering capital market growth and development, the SEC has devised a number of means to achieve this:

Policy Initiation: This first and perhaps most important is the initiation of government policies relating to the capital market. In this regard, the SEC takes advantage to its position as the chief adviser to the government on matters affecting the capital market. Since it was established, the SEC has initiated a number of policies which are today successful government programme. For instance, the SEC, in realization of the positive impact which privatization and debt conversion programmes can have on the capital market and the national economy, decided to stimulate

interest in the subject, creating appropriate fora for critical examination of these subjects. The eventual outcome was the introduction of privatization and debt conversion programmes by the government.

The privatization programme which is still undergoing implementation has particularly stimulated growth of the market. In the four years of its introduction, shares of over Volume 5 twenty two companies have been divested through the instrumentality of the Niger Stock Exchange and more are in the pipeline for privatization through similar means. The programme has also enlarge the share owners base in the country as mo Nigerians now invest in the stock market while increases capital market awareness has been observed in the country.

In many developing countries, the low income level of the citizens, and the lack of skill for direct portfolio management, dampens interest in the capital market. As way of o of this problem, the SEC initiated the laws (administere by it) which regulated unit trust schemes in Nigeria. At the moment there are about eleven unit trust scheme operating in the country with assets running into millions of naira and enhance participation in the market. Of recent the SEC granted Approval for the flotation of the first investment trust company to be quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange. Thes instruments, the SEC believes would serve as stimuli for market development as they would ease both the demand for and supply of securities.

In the areas of status, the SEC has been instrumental in initiating changes to existin laws, and drafting of new laws to foster capital market development.

It is known that fiscal and other incentives have been extensively employed to boo: some emerging capital markets. Market authorities in Nigeria are left in no dout about the desirability of introducing same in Nigeria. Such measures would requir amendment to existing laws. The SEC has persistently (as far back as 1980) advocate for the application of market incentives to the Nigerian Market. So also has the Nigeria Stock Exchange. As a response as an initials, step withholding tax on capital marke instruments was recently reduced from 15 percent to 5 percent.

In the submission of policy proposals to government, regulatory authorities shoul ensure that such proposals are well articulated and convincing enough to warran positive response most of the time. There is no gainsaying the fact that othe considerations (such as envisaged revenue loss) could influence government decision in granting incentives to the capital market; that notwithstanding, regulatory authorities should be ablé to properly educate government on the

benefits of incentives and other policy proposals which might originate from the proper understanding on the issues by government could yield favourable response.

Public Awareness: A capital market-literate society is no doubt an asset to its growth and development. In Nigeria, the public is largely uneducated about the essence, working and benefits of the capital market. This situation makes it imperative for the SEC, the Nigerian Stock Exchange and Market operators to vigorously embark on programmes aimed at improving knowledge about the capital market. The most widely used method for public education has been the creation of public fora such as seminars, conferences, and workshops etc where issues of the capital markets are discussed. From observation most participants at such gatherings usually have good knowledge of the working of the market and do attend to broaden their knowledge on sometimes specialized issues. Thus most participants have largely been market operators, government functionaries, the academic community, professional bodies and staff of quoted companies. While these meetings have not been too successful in attracting grassroots participation, they have been very valuable in discussing issues aimed at improving the professional expertise of operators, the operational efficiency of the market, listing on the Stock Exchange, introduction of new financial instruments etc. Decisions reached at every such gathering organized by the SEC are a matter of policy made available to the government for necessary action. The privatization, debt conversion and unit trusts all formed subjects of SEC conferences. Proceedings of such fora are usually given considerable publicity for effective dissemination of information on issues discussed and decisions reached to the general public. To date, the SEC has sponsored over twenty public awareness fora.

The use of the media (both print and electronic) is probably the most effective means of reaching the grassroots. The SEC has on occasions used this avenue successfully. For effective dissemination of information relating to capital market to the public, the SEC strongly believes that the media community is invaluable. However, for proper reporting, good understanding of the capital market is essential. The SEC therefore occasionally organizes enlightenment programmes for financial journalists. In addition, information on the market are regularly made available to them for onward dissemination to the public.

Another very vital method of enhancing public knowledge which has been proved to be useful is the publication of a variety of market related periodicals, pamphlets and conference proceedings etc. These publications are technical and non-technical to cater for various

categories of readers. A video documentary film on the market has also been produced by the SEC as a public education material.

In 1991, at the instance of the SEC a Capital Market Committee (CMC) comprising representatives of the SEC and market operators was set-up. The CMC which is purely an advisory body meets on quarterly basis to discuss issues affecting the capital market and when problems are identified, the CMC proffers solutions to such problems. Subcommittees are established when necessary to examine specific issues. Two subcommittees were for instance established, one of which is to look into the modalities for operating in an over-the-counter market in the country. It is our belief than an over the counter market would activate the market considerably.

The Nigerian Stock Exchange: The regulatory roles of the SEC and the Nigerian Stock Exchange are complementary. As a self-regulatory organization (SRO) the Stock Exchange has authority over its members to whom it sets rules of ethics to guide their professional behaviour. The rules, professional behaviour. The rules which must be approved by the SEC, incorporate expected behaviour of members on and off the trading floors. Such rules and regulations are aimed at ensuring orderliness on the trading floor, honesty of stockbrokers in dealing with client and among themselves, preventing conflict of interest, and generally upholding the market's integrity and protecting the interest of the public.

The Nigerian Stock Exchange, like others, believes in the principle "**MY WORD IS MY BOND**" which must be imbibed by all is dealing members. To deal on the trading floor, stock broker must have successfully undergone a training period of six (6) months, after which he takes the Stock Exchange qualifying examination which comprises both written and oral assessment. This is necessary to prevent incompetence in securities trading. Since only brokers authorized by the Stock Exchange and registered by the SEC can deal in listed securities, investors are assured that necessary steps have been taken to safeguard their interest. They are also assured that agents found wanting would be appropriately dealt with by the Stock Exchange and it necessary by the SEC. Usually, the SEC would intervene if it considers the stock exchange's sanction on a member firm inadequate for the offence committed. That aside, the power and responsibilities of the SEC are much wider and so also are the measures it can take against violators of the securities laws. The awareness of all these, gives investors some level of confidence to invest in securities.

The regulatory powers of Stock Exchange transcends its members. It has its purview issuers of listed securities who must meet certain laid down criteria before their securities can be accepted for listing and to remain listed. Most of the listing requirements are intended to protect existing and potential shareholders of the company. The Exchange therefore, requires that full and material information on operators of quoted companies be made available to shareholders at regular intervals. Material changes must however be immediately released to the exchanges for transaction to brokers, although the responsibility of market development falls principally on the SEC, the Nigerian Stock Exchange as an SRO, and a major player in the market also has the duty of increasing public knowledge towards enhanced participation in the market place.

To its credit the exchange had embarked on numerous public enlightenment programmes and publishes a number of public information materials. An important feat of the Exchange was the introduction of a Second tier Securities Market (SSM) in 1985 to attract the quotation of smaller companies not ripe for quotation on the main board. There are currently twenty companies on this market while three have graduated to this market while three have graduated to the main board.

Conclusion: There is no doubt that the existence of both Securities and Exchange Commission and the Nigerian Stock Exchange, as joint regulators of capital market has had positive influence on the market. Although growth had been slow in some areas, remarkable progress has been recorded in others. The number of quoted companies has increased from three at inception of the Stock Exchange in 1961 to 146 as at middle of September 1992 an average of four listing a year. This might not look impressive, but, government policies in recent years coupled with the activities of the regulatory bodies has encouraged listing remarkably. For instance between 1985 and September 15, 1992 fifty new equities were listed on the Stock Exchange

The market has also become an important source of new capital to business entities as new issued raised in the capital market reached almost N10 billion at the beginning of the 1990s. Market operators have only increased, but have become more efficient and innovative. The level of professionalism has also evidently improved. Although infrastructural problems still plague the market, improvement is being made. The Stock Exchange has for instance recorded

THE ROLE OF REGULATORY BODIES IN CAPITAL MARKET DEVELOPMENT:

THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE

progress towards improving the clearing and settlement process. Finally, the level of market awareness has increased remarkably as more Nigerians now show interest in the capital market.

THE ROLE OF REGULATORY BODIES IN CAPITAL MARKET DEVELOPMENT:

THE NIGERIAN EXPERIENCE

REFERENCES

Camemu R (1972) Banking and Economic Development

Central Bank of Nigeria (2004) Annual Report

Ekpenyong D.B.F (1994) Financial Distress in Banks Nature And Implication

Onwinmere JUJ (1992) The Nigeria Financial Markets An Approval Nigerian Financial Review

CBN Bullion Nigeria Capital Markets

Ajayi S.I. (1995) The Role of Central Bank In Economic Development CB Economic and Financial Review

CBN (1979) Twenty Years of Central Bank In Nigeria